

Islamic Movements / Secular Governments: Competing Visions of Governance

By: Louloua Awad

In the decades following the collapse of empire, Muslim-majority states faced the urgent task of defining sovereignty on their own terms. From Cairo to Tehran to Jakarta and Lahore, intellectuals and revolutionaries sought not only political independence, but moral and cultural legitimacy in the aftermath of colonization, humiliation, and internal fragmentation. While secular nationalism initially promised modernization and unity, its failure to deliver justice or dignity opened space for the revival of political Islam, not as a stagnant or purely theological force but as an adaptive and strategic project rooted in historical and political interpretation. Everyone, whether Islamist or secularist, was speaking the language of sovereignty, yet each did so through a different reading of their history, shaped by the specific political, colonial, and ideological fractures of their nation.

Despite facing similar questions of reclaiming legitimacy, these states' political conditions varied dramatically. Some inherited deep colonial entanglements or endured violent transitions; others negotiated independence through inclusive, broad-based movements. The extent to which religion was suppressed, co-opted, or integrated into the new state project shaped whether Islamism would radicalize in opposition or remain morally embedded, as a dynamic response to national disappointment, cultural alienation, and the search for post-imperial meaning. Through a comparative analysis of Sayyid Qutb, Ali Shariati, Muhammad Iqbal, and President Sukarno, this paper explores how Islamic and secular visions of the state reflect divergent responses to shared crises, and how each thinker reimagined the role of Islam in rebuilding sovereignty, identity, and moral order.

In Egypt, where British colonialism gave way to Nasser's authoritarian secular nationalism, Sayyid Qutb developed a militant version of Islam as the only legitimate basis for sovereignty, justice, and social order. Secular governance first under colonial rule and then under the Free Officers, had failed to deliver dignity or independence. The 1948 Arab-Israeli War, in which Egyptian forces returned humiliated, and the earlier suppression of nationalist movements like the Wafd Party, revealed the

hollowness of nationalist promises. Qutb's work, written during his imprisonment after Nasser's crackdown on the Muslim Brotherhood, was not a theological reflection but a revolutionary indictment of modernity, including Western, secular, and even nominally Islamic, as complicit in a global descent into jahiliyya (ignorance). For Qutb, the world had "repudiated Allah's hakimiyya (sovereignty)" and instead surrendered to "man's authority", through nationalism, socialism, and liberal democracy (Qutb, 131). He saw secular regimes like Nasser's which adopted the outward forms of Western modernity without moral foundations as sacrilegious. After returning from a U.S. government-sponsored trip in 1948, Qutb found in American society confirmation of his fears: it was "racist, sexually promiscuous, reflexively pro-Israeli, and morally impoverished" (Qutb, 130). But it was Egypt's own embrace of those values under the banner of Arab socialism that radicalized him. When Nasser banned the Brotherhood and imprisoned thousands, including Qutb, he saw secular modernity, whether Western or Arab, as spiritually bankrupt: "Humanity today is standing at the brink of an abyss," he warned, "not because of the threat of annihilation ... but because humanity is bankrupt in the realm of "values"" (Qutb, 136). The West had lost its claim to moral authority and secular Arab leaders were simply replicating its failure. Hence, Qutb did not advocate reform but a complete societal rupture. True Islam, he argued, was the solution and compromise with secular culture was impossible: "We and it [jahiliyya] are on different paths and if we happen to accompany it for one step, we will lose our way entirely" (Qutb, 144). His solution was a vanguard with a disciplined elite to confront and dismantle secularism through jihad, not merely violent, but precise and ideological. This was not nostalgia for the caliphate or a return to lost glory, but a future-oriented political project that positioned Islamism as the only path to reclaim dignity, authority, purpose, and postcolonial sovereignty.

In 1970s Iran, where a U.S.-backed monarchy imposed rapid modernization through force, Ali Shariati presented a radical Islamic humanism designed to reclaim Iran's cultural authenticity and dignity from both foreign domination and domestic repression. The Shah's White Revolution promised progress but delivered alienation, involving massive land reforms, rural education programs, and Westernization initiatives, which concentrated power in the monarchy, enriched a narrow elite, and marginalized the

religious and rural poor. Amid this political dislocation and spiritual fragmentation, Shariati, writing to a young, educated, and increasingly disillusioned generation, warned that Iran's "modernized" identity was an illusion imposed by global capitalism "under the guise of civilizing nations" and has severed Muslims from their own history, religion, and background (Shariati, 1). Shariati saw this cultural rupture as the deepest wound of imperialism, not just the loss of land or oil, but this internalization of inferiority. He claims Iran, like other Muslim nations, has become "mosaic societies," pieced together from "some leftover parts from the past, some deformed parts from Europe" (Shariati, 6-7) creating "a shapeless, aimless society". This loss of identity, he argued, was not accidental but engineered. Western modernity, marketed as "civilization" was designed to create desire for Western goods, values and lifestyles while destroying the confidence of non-European peoples in their own traditions. Hence, Shariati's tone is unsparing and urgent. He insists modernization turned Muslims into "second-hand personalities," consumers of European ideas and products, no longer capable of choosing for themselves (Shariati, 12). Against this, Shariati doesn't call for a return to traditionalism but for an intellectual revolution grounded in Islam's original moral purpose. Unlike Qutb, Shariati's critique was not directed at secularism, but at the co-opted, Westernized political elite, including the Shah and his court, who used secular rhetoric to suppress opposition, ban independent parties, and align Iran with U.S. interests during the Cold War.

Unlike Egypt or Iran, post-independence Indonesia under Sukarno embraced an inclusive secular nationalism that positioned Islam as a vital part of national identity, not its political foundation. Under Sukarno's leadership, Islam was honored culturally but not enforced by the state, reflecting Indonesia's unique context: a vast, multiethnic archipelago with diverse religions and regional histories. In contrast to Egypt's suppression of Islamist groups or Iran's Westernizing monarchy, Indonesia's independence was won through a shared anti-colonial struggle between secular and Islamic groups. At the 1955 Bandung Conference, Sukarno affirmed this pluralism: "It is not an Islam Conference, nor a Christian Conference,...It is not an exclusive club either...Rather it is a body of enlightened, tolerant opinion which seeks to impress on the world that all men and all countries have their place under the sun" (Sukarno, 5). This inclusive vision was solidified during the 1945 constitutional debates, when Sukarno and other

nationalist leaders removed a proposed clause mandating Islamic law (the Jakarta Charter) to preserve unity in a religiously diverse nation. Here, secularism was not a rejection of Islam but a strategy to prevent division and defend its sovereignty. The founding principle, “Bhinneka Tunggal Ika - Unity in Diversity,” framed national identity as inclusive rather than sectarian (Sukarno, 6). Unlike in Egypt or Iran, Islamic parties in Indonesia like Muhammadiyah and Nahdlatul Ulama, were allowed to operate after independence and were not violently suppressed. Sukarno’s secularism, shaped by Cold War pressures, also positioned Indonesia against both capitalist and communist blocs, favoring Asian-African solidarity as he declared: “what is the highest code of morality? It is the subordination of everything to the well-being of mankind”(Sukarno, 2). In Indonesia, where secularism emerged from a shared anti-colonial ethic, religion and nationalism could coexist and protect Indonesia’s unity, preventing political Islam from becoming revolutionary.

Colonial India and post-partition Pakistan, had Muhammad Iqbal envisioning Islam not as a theocratic mandate, but as a moral and political ideal capable of uniting Muslims, resisting Hindu majoritarianism, and grounding a sovereign Pakistani identity. His work emerged from the crisis of the British Raj’s divide and rule tactics, growing Hindu dominance in the Indian National Congress, and the marginalization of Muslim identity within secular nationalist discourse. For Iqbal, Muslims had become both politically disempowered and spiritually enervated, not only through imperial subjugation but through internal disunity. He wrote, “Surely we have out-Hindued the Hindu himself,” adopting “the religious caste system, sectarianism, and the social caste system” and forgetting egalitarian foundations of Islam (Iqbal, 312). Iqbal’s solution was not clericalism but ethical reawakening. He rejected sectarianism claiming, “There are no Wahhabis, Shi’is, Mirza’is, or Sunnis in Islam” calling such divisions colonial legacies and mere “interpretations” of the truth that undermined the ummah’s unity (Iqbal, 313). For Muslims without territorial sovereignty, he argued nationhood must be rooted in belief and shared moral vision, not geography. This idea laid the foundation for his 1930 address to the Muslim League, where he proposed a separate Muslim homeland in northwest India, an early philosophical basis for Pakistan. Crucially, his vision contrasted with the Congress Party’s secular liberalism, which he saw as incapable of

guaranteeing Muslim dignity in a Hindu-majority state. Instead, Iqbal imagined an Islamic democracy in which “man develop all the possibilities of his nature by allowing him as much freedom as practicable,” advocating personal liberty and collective ethical responsibility (Iqbal, 311). Islamism in this region was not anti-modern or rigid, it was open-ended, anti-sectarian, and deeply political. In a region fractured by Partition and deep ethnic and linguistic divides, Iqbal offered Islam as a unifying source of postcolonial sovereignty, one that resisted both Western materialism and the cultural dominance of Indian secular nationalism.

The political trajectories of Egypt, Iran, Indonesia, and Pakistan in the wake of empire varied widely, and shaped fundamentally different visions of the role of Islam in the modern nation-state. Qutb’s thought is deeply shaped by Egypt’s unique colonial experience: a failed liberal nationalist experiment, a secular militarized turn, and a deeply unequal socioeconomic order. Islamism became militant, to combat authoritarianism, and was a revolutionary necessity that sought not to coexist with the nation, but to replace it. In Iran, decades of foreign economic interference and the 1953 CIA-backed coup against Prime Minister Mossadegh created deep distrust toward both Western liberalism and the Shah’s rapid secularization. These conditions led Ali Shariati to develop a revolutionary form of Islamism that combined Shi’ism with anti-imperialist and socialist critique, reclaiming sovereignty through cultural authenticity and ethical revival. In contrast, Indonesia’s inclusive nationalism, grounded in religious pluralism and anti-colonial solidarity, allowed secularism and Islam to coexist, preventing Islamism from becoming radicalized. Meanwhile, in India and Pakistan, Iqbal responded to both colonial erasure and Hindu majoritarianism by integrating Islam into national life. Here, Muhammad Iqbal envisioned Islam as a unifying moral framework, one capable of sustaining spiritual dignity and political identity without demanding clerical rule, for a new kind of sovereignty.

Across all four regions, Islamism did not emerge as a universal ideology but as a local response to secular failure, imperial betrayal, or cultural alienation. In Egypt and Iran, where secularism was imposed from above and entangled with authoritarianism or foreign influence, Islamism turned revolutionary. Qutb wrote to a population brutalized by state repression and military defeat, advocating total rejection.

Shariati, by contrast, addressed an urban, Western-educated youth alienated by cultural mimicry and monarchy, using revolutionary language to reclaim identity and moral agency. In Indonesia, where secularism developed through inclusive anti-colonial consensus, political Islam remained integrative rather than oppositional. As for Pakistan, Islam served as a unifying ideal in the absence of ethnic cohesion learnt from India, offering a philosophical foundation for nationhood rather than a legalistic framework. Each vision responded not only to political conditions but to distinct publics, whether victims of violence, cultural disinheritance, or fragmentation. In every case, Islamism was not simply a rejection of secularism, but a strategic and moral effort to rebuild sovereignty through the language of faith.

The legacies of these thinkers continue to shape political Islam today, not as relics of the past but as evolving frameworks for power, legitimacy, and identity. In Egypt, Qutb's legacy haunts the present: the Muslim Brotherhood remains outlawed, and the state uses the specter of Islam to justify ongoing authoritarianism. In Iran, Shariati's revolutionary idealism helped pave the way for the 1979 Islamic Revolution, yet the current regime's repression has led many of the same urban youth he once inspired to reject both clerical authority and Western intervention. Indonesia remains the region's clearest example of Islamic pluralism, though rising populist pressures have tested its secular foundations in recent years. In Pakistan, Iqbal's philosophical Islamism continues to resonate in political rhetoric, even as the state oscillates between democratic aspirations and militarized religion. Each case reflects not a singular Islamic politics, but a living struggle to reconcile modern statehood with moral legitimacy. Political Islam endures, not as an alternative to modernity, but as a mirror of its failure and a language through which many still imagine justice.

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